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Research Article

**FORENSIC EXAMINATIONS IN CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS:
PROBLEMS OF LAW ENFORCEMENT**¹Y. Demidchenko, ²O. Paliyeva, ³V. Paliyev, ⁴B. Tcoi¹Rostov branch of Russian State University of Justice», Rostov-on-Don, Russia.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

The article analyzes the procedure for the appointment and production of forensic examination in the course of the investigation of criminal cases and their consideration in court. Procedural violations committed by officials of the preliminary investigation bodies when appointing forensic examinations, the low level of their production by forensic experts, the contradictory conclusions of experts, are often grounds for the appointment of additional and repeated examinations in a criminal case. The rationale for the relevance of the study of this problem on the basis of the analysis of existing legal acts. The features of the implementation of the rules governing the institution of purpose and examination in criminal proceedings with examples of investigative and judicial practice are indicated. Suggested solutions to solve problems.

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INTRODUCTION:

The practice of criminal justice shows that there has recently been a significant increase in the appointment and production of forensic examinations in the framework of the investigation of criminal cases. This is due, above all, to the increased capacity of expert institutions, as well as the urgent need of the preliminary investigation authorities to quickly obtain evidence in the ways that the criminal procedure law gives them. The Code of Criminal Procedure provides for an expert opinion (part 2 of article 74 of the Code of Criminal Procedure) as evidence in a criminal case.

Obtaining this type of evidence has become an integral part of criminal proceedings in the investigation of all types of crimes, but most often in criminal cases related to the investigation of murders, sexual crimes, road traffic accidents, injury to health and so on.

The presence in the criminal case of the expert's opinion at the initial stage of the investigation of the criminal case gives the investigator the confidence in the correctness of the chosen direction of the investigation. A professional investigator, having received the expert's opinion on the difficult key point, will diligently analyze the logic of the expert research and its conclusions.

Thus, he receives not only full answers to the questions asked by the investigation, but also a tool for the further development of the tactics and strategy of the investigation of the criminal case.

Often, participants in legal proceedings, including officials, are mistaken about the importance of a forensic examination and, without sufficient reason to do so, define it with the most important evidence, ignoring other possibilities of proving circumstances in a criminal case.

The expert opinion as evidence is found in the vast majority of criminal cases. In a significant part of the cases several forensic examinations are carried out. This takes into account the high level of special knowledge of experts and the application of scientific and technical techniques that have been scaled up in practice. There is no doubt that expert research is one of the most important evidence in a criminal case, but not the main one.

The purpose of the study: the study of expertise as the main form of use of special knowledge in criminal proceedings, features of the procedural order of appointment and production of forensic

examinations, assessment of expert opinion by an official in order to eliminate contradictory conclusions that lead to an erroneous qualification of crimes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted on the basis of a hermeneutic analysis of regulatory documents, investigative and judicial practice. In conducting the study, various methods of cognition, interpretation, systematization and synthesis of information were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In recent years, the quality of forensic examinations has deteriorated markedly. This is evidenced by the fact that in a single criminal case, the findings of several forensic examinations appointed: primary, repeated, commission, commission complex can easily contradict each other. And such cases are everyday.

For example, in a criminal case initiated under Part 1 of Art. 264 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation in connection with the injury to health resulting from an accident, in the process of its investigation three forensic medical examinations were appointed. Two of them were commissions. In each of the three, the question of determining the severity of injuries caused as a result of an accident by the victim K.E.A. In all cases, the diagnosis of a health disorder, the duration of treatment, and the result of recovery were the same. However, the conclusions of the experts and the conclusions they give on the determination of the severity of harm to health are completely different. In one of the examinations, an extra-alkaline fracture of the humerus was qualified as a serious injury to health, and in the other two - as a injury of moderate severity [11]. Experts qualified the same damage to the humerus according to different points of the "Rules for Determining the Severity of Harm Caused to Human Health" approved by Resolution of the Government of the Russian Federation of August 17, 2007 No. 522, paragraph 7.1 "Medical Criteria for Determining the Severity of Harm Caused to Human Health" approved by order No. 194n of the Ministry of Health and Social Development of the Russian Federation of April 24, 2008 [4]. From the analysis of the course of commission expert studies, the incompleteness and unreliability of the studies performed are seen. The experts in their conclusions directly contradicted the principles of applying and interpreting the provisions of the Rules given by leading experts of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation V. Klevno and Bogomolova I.N.,

who directly led the development of these rules.

In such cases, the investigation and then the court has reasonable doubts either about the quality of education and special training of forensic experts, or about the suitability of the normative act "Rules for determining the severity of harm to human health" for use in everyday judicial practice and interpretation by ordinary experts.

As for the aforementioned concrete criminal case, the investigator did not begin to delve into the meaning and depth of the experts' disagreements and issued a decision to terminate the criminal case, for lack of c. V.I.N. corpus delicti. And lost health and violated rights of the victim K.E.A. in this case, now only the victim is concerned. The defense continues to attempt to appeal the decision of the official, together with the existing expert opinions [11].

Another example from the case file. The victim K. claimed that his neighbors B. and K. struck him with a baseball bat in the region of the knee joint, causing injury to the body. From the conclusion of the forensic medical examination it follows that the injured K. was injured in the left knee joint in the form of a closed intra-articular multi-fragment depressed fracture of the outer epimethadiaphysis of the left tibia with an offset, accompanied by damage to the external meniscus. The expert's conclusion states that the injury was caused by a wooden baseball bat. Harm to the victim is qualified as serious.

In the conclusion of the re-commissioned complex forensic examination by other forensic experts, it was concluded that the injury could not have been caused by a wooden bat. This is confirmed by the local nature of the fracture. Harm to the victim is qualified as serious.

In the third additional commission complex examination, the commission of experts came to the conclusion that it was not possible to determine objectively by expert means: how the damage was caused. But the harm to health is qualified as average.

Which of the above examinations the court will be able to consider reliable and complete as required by the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation?

In investigative and judicial practice there are many problems not only with the production of forensic examinations, but also with their purpose. Officials, when appointing a forensic examination, should know the legal status and organizational forms of

forensic examinations, which are regulated by Federal Law No. 73-FZ of May 31, 2001 "On State Forensic Expert Activities in the Russian Federation" (hereinafter referred to as the Law on the CSED) Order No. 346n of the Ministry of Health and Social Development of the Russian Federation dated May 12, 2010 "On approval of the procedure for organizing and conducting forensic medical examinations in state forensic institutions of the Russian Federation" and Resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation dated December 21, 2010 № 28 "On forensic expertise in criminal cases."

In accordance with Art. 7 of the SSED Law "forensic examination is a procedural action consisting of conducting research and giving an opinion by an expert on issues whose resolution requires special knowledge in the field of science, technology, art or craft, and which are put before an expert by a court, judge, inquiry body, person investigating investigator in order to establish the circumstances to be proved in a particular case."

In the concept of forensic examination expressed its essence, and therefore its differences from other types of examinations (research). The essence of the forensic examination is to conduct a study by an authorized expert, by decision of the cognizant, the investigator and the court, with the provision of tangible objects in the form of physical evidence and criminal case materials. The purpose of the examination is to establish the circumstances relevant to the criminal case.

It follows from the above that a forensic examination should be carried out by an expert on the basis of the decision (determination) of the official in charge of the investigation or consideration of the criminal case.

An important circumstance is the mandatory expert warning of criminal liability under art. 307 of the Criminal Code. Such a forensic examination is evidence in accordance with paragraph 3 of Part 2 of Art. 73 Code of Criminal Procedure.

Enforcement practice shows that the forensic examination carried out in the state expert institution is more weighty evidence in comparison with the expertise performed by a non-governmental expert, since the status of the last year's court is less significant. In Part 1 of Art. 195 Code of Criminal Procedure, the legislator pays attention to this. "Forensic examination is carried out by state judicial experts and other experts from among persons with

special knowledge."

The phrase "other experts" indicates, as it were, the "secondary importance" of the status of non-state experts.

However, the activities of non-state experts are governed by the same Law on the CSED, in particular, Art. 2, 4, 6-8, 16-17, h. 2 tbsp. 18, art. 24-25 in which they are subject to procedural legislation governing the institution of forensic examination in criminal proceedings.

Consequently, state and non-state judicial experts in the production of forensic examinations have the same legal status. Accordingly, the expert opinions prepared by both state and non-state judicial experts are equally valid.

In Art. 204 of the Code of Criminal Procedure specifies the requirements for an expert's opinion. The completeness and clarity of a forensic examination largely depends on the professional preparedness and integrity of an expert.

For a state expert who performs forensic examinations in the framework of official assignments, the level of material incentives for quality work is lower than that of non-state ones, and the level of responsibility is higher.

The level of expert qualifications of non-state experts is no lower than that of state experts (often they are "former" experts of state expert institutions, for example, those who retired from expert institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs). Such experts have a direct interest in the highest quality performance of the assigned forensic examination in order to receive a fee and maintain the authority of the expert organization.

When appointing a forensic examination and choosing an expert institution, it is necessary to clarify: the expert's qualifications (licenses or admission), the availability of relevant "expert" training, the total length of expert work, experience in conducting expert examinations on these objects, the availability and level of technical equipment, using which examination will be performed. Only if all these conditions are met, the court will be able to get full and reasonable answers to the questions put to the expert.

Law-enforcement practice shows that when assigning examinations, investigators pose general, "sample" and extremely "formalized" questions to experts. In other cases, on the contrary, the investigators, when formulating the questions, provoke the expert to go beyond his competence. It must always be

remembered that the questions posed to the expert must be formulated clearly, clearly and unequivocally. The stage of preparation of the examination is not difficult for investigators in cases where they use the opportunity to obtain preliminary consultations from experts as specialists prior to the appointment of the examination itself.

The handling of physical evidence, especially of biological origin, at the stage of detection and removal during the inspection of the scene, their selection from the participants of the process, and sending them to the study causes fair criticism of experts. This applies to the actions of persons not procedurally defined by the criminal procedure law, in particular, police officers who, at the inquiry stage without obtaining the consent and permission of the investigator, independently withdraw material evidence from the scene and send them to various expert institutions. Often, the investigators themselves withdraw from the scene of the incident and, without a proper assessment, send everything that can be investigated. At the same time, they act independently, without waiting for the medical examiner to arrive at the scene of the incident. For the same reason, at the scene of the incident, the investigators did not detect, describe or withdraw the necessary amount of blood traces that could help determine the regional origin of the bleeding, the position of the victim at the time of injury, the height of the blood spot formation due to her mind, etc. Investigators simply do not find these traces, take them for stains of non-blood origin. Difficulties are cases where suspects are trying to destroy the traces of the crime.

Too late submission to the examination of physical evidence of biological origin entails the irretrievable loss of biological signs. The absence or late submission of comparative samples of blood, urine, saliva, control gauze also reduces the possibility of examination.

In this regard, it is impossible not to agree with P.K. Gadzhiramazanova, who writes: "It is not uncommon for different objects to be put together in one package (for example, clothes from the victim's corpse, together with the clothes of the suspect), while one of the questions submitted for expert permission is the question of possible contact interaction between the objects."

So far, there have been cases of untimely familiarization of participants in criminal proceedings with the resolution on the appointment of an examination. The Plenum of the Supreme Court of

the Russian Federation has long indicated these shortcomings. For example, in paragraph 9 of the Decree No. 28 of December 21, 2010 "On Forensic Examination in Criminal Cases" it was stated that it was necessary "to explain to the courts that the suspect, the accused and their defense lawyers, as well as the victim, should be familiarized with the resolution on the appointment of an examination before production. Despite this, officials acquaint suspects (defendants), their defenders, victims and their representatives after receiving the results of the examinations. This remains a problem of the observance of legality by the investigators and explains the significant volume of the relevant complaints from the above participants in the criminal process.

The right of participants in criminal proceedings to withdraw an expert is not always respected. One of the main reasons for this situation is the imperfection of the criminal procedure legislation. So, in art. 195 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation, there is a requirement according to which the investigator indicates in the order for the appointment of an examination the surname, name and patronymic of the expert or the name of the expert institution in which it is planned to conduct a forensic examination. However, the duty is not fixed when it is impossible to make an examination in this institution, to make a decision on the appointment of an examination in another expert institution. Without having this information available to the participant in the criminal process, it is impossible for the defense to understand all the circumstances and the course of the relevant criminal case. On this basis, we propose to add Art. 195 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation with part 1.1 of the following content: "If it is impossible to carry out an examination in this institution, a decision is issued on the appointment of an examination in another expert institution".

Essential for the emergence of doubts about the objectivity of the execution of individual examinations, in particular forensic research, causes the territorial principle of research, enshrined in Art. 11 of the Federal Law of May 31, 2001 No. 73-FZ "On State Forensic Expert Activities in the Russian Federation". It is imperatively established that "state forensic institutions must necessarily conduct forensic examinations for inquiry agencies, preliminary investigators and courts located in the territory that is determined by the relevant federal executive bodies" [3], as well as by the Order of the Ministry of Health and Social Development No. 346n of May 12, 2010 "On Approving the Procedure for

Organizing and Conducting Forensic Medical Examinations in State Forensic Expert Institutions of the Russian Federation", and P stopping the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation of December 21, 2010 No. 28 "On forensic examination in criminal cases".

A significant part of practicing lawyers had a well-founded opinion that the territorial relationship between health authorities, experts of the FMS Bureau and the security forces of the Russian Federation, and sometimes personal acquaintance of staff, friendly relations, and cronyism cannot positively affect the objectivity of expert research. "In the investigation of criminal cases on the facts of inappropriate professional actions of medical workers, appointed expert studies in the BSME of the Ministry of Health in the overwhelming majority of cases do not give a satisfying result ... because of the "corporate nature" of the medical environment, since it is well known that simultaneous management and medical institutions, and BSME are carried out by the Healthcare Committees of the respective subjects of the Russian Federation".

The courts, in deciding on the appointment of such examinations, almost without exception make decisions on the appointment of forensic medical examinations to other subjects of the Russian Federation. It seems to us that the current practice of extraterritoriality of conducting examinations that are significant for the investigation should be enshrined in law.

The quality of the performance of forensic examinations can be traced back to their content: numerous errors, in the form of technical clues, confused names of suspects and defendants, plot of criminal cases copied from other criminal cases, errors in calculations, references applicable guidelines, etc., attract attention. Such inconsistencies in the examination conclusions are administratively punishable for the expert (reprimand, other punishment). In assessing the conclusion of the court itself, it is usually indicated that the expert had made a technical error, which was not influenced by the substance of the criminal case. If it is strictly necessary to follow the letter of the law, then such evidence must be recognized in court as invalid evidence in accordance with Art. 75 Code of Criminal Procedure.

It remains the same unresolved question of how the court should deal with examinations in which the experts' conclusions contradict each other, or during the court session it is established that the experts'

conclusions are based on inaccurate data. In such cases, the court is forced by its inner conviction to “choose” from several conclusions the most appropriate. We consider it mandatory to legislatively establish a single algorithm for the actions of the investigator and the court in the event of a conflict of views and opinions of experts.

As an option, we consider it possible to offer compulsory interrogation of experts in court, each separately, and then in the form of their cross-examination. At the same time, the parties to the process retain the right to invite professors, associate professors of universities, leading specialists of research institutes, and consultants from independent forensic examinations as independent experts to the court session.

In the legislation of the Russian Federation there is no indication of the body authorized to monitor the activities of forensic experts and the quality of their examinations. As a result, experts with a low level of knowledge and for other reasons, including the corruption component, make inaccurate conclusions on the study, absolutely do not worry about the consequences of their work. Behind every fact of such unlawful imprisonment stands fate, health, and sometimes human life, as well as not establishing the truth in a criminal case.

According to Art. 89 of the Federal Law of November 21, 2011 No. 323-FZ “On the Basics of Health Protection of Citizens in the Russian Federation”, the executive authorities of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation carry out departmental control over the activities of bodies and organizations subordinate to them. Departmental control includes conducting inspections of compliance by medical organizations with the procedures and standards of medical care; safe working conditions, requirements for the safe use and operation of medical devices; compliance with all medical and pharmaceutical workers restrictions in the implementation of professional activities. The implementation of control and supervisory measures by the executive authorities of the Russian Federation in the field of health in relation to expert activities of state medical expert organizations with analysis and making policy comments on the assessment of the validity of expert opinions, leading to the inevitable impact on the findings of the IEM, is legally impossible.

From our point of view, the society has long overdue the need to create an institution of independent medical experts. This is connected not only with the

problems of the appointment of examinations by the investigation and the court, but also with the quality of their implementation. Independent expertise is also needed to establish the quality of medical care and treatment provided. A citizen has the right to apply for the fact that he was provided with insufficiently qualified medical aid, as well as for the actions of the doctor if in his opinion there is a medical error. The actions of the doctor and the nursing staff today are evaluated by lawyers, investigators and judges, those who do not even have basic knowledge in the health care system or in the rules for rendering medical aid. This is an abnormal situation for a developed, civilized society. Even a medical expert cannot always assess the quality of an operation carried out using a unique technology, or when the attending physician takes a conscious risk to save the patient's life. The doctor still at the institute is afraid of responsibility as such. But today, doctors are compelled to total, indiscriminate responsibility for any unfavorable result, even in the case when everything was done in the best possible way, and the unfavorable result was the inevitable and logical consequence of the disease and the possibilities of medicine.

The lack of the necessary knowledge of this or other type of forensic examination of the majority of the participants in court proceedings does not allow persons conducting an investigation or consideration of cases to objectively assess the conclusions reached by the expert. Therefore, during the trial, it often becomes necessary to invite experts to a meeting to explain their conclusions on the questions put to them. Judicial and medical examinations of an independent objective assessment by the judicial staff of events and facts of rendering medical assistance, as well as a correct interpretation of expert opinions made, is a priori impossible due to the lack of medical education judges.

In the practice of the investigation and the court, there are often situations in which specialists from different fields of medicine give explanations to the parties and the court about the conclusions contained in the opinion of the forensic expert and within their competence. Often such situations arise when the court assesses the findings of the commission of forensic medical examinations on the materials of criminal cases, including cases related to the inappropriate performance of professional duties by doctors.

We believe that the state of forensic medical examinations on “medical” disputes does not meet the requirements of the legal procedure. The main burden in this matter now lies with the courts - they

are the ones who assess the expertise according to the criteria of admissibility, reliability and relevance of the opinion. In this regard, it should be noted that it is the courts that must more specifically determine what is to be obtained from a forensic medical examination in a particular case. Therefore, it is necessary to formulate the questions for the expert as clearly as possible, not to allow vagueness of formulations and repetitions. Define the boundaries of the concepts of legal and medical, it will not prevent the initiative of forensic experts.

Often, judges, due to their workload or for other reasons, simply do not try to delve into the essence of the research conducted by the expert. For example, when entering the analysis of evidence in the verdict of the court, it is noted that the conclusions of the expert "are consistent" with other evidence. If, for example, the defense does not agree with the conclusions of the expert, then the decision states that "the conclusions of the expert do not contradict other evidence."

An expert opinion, like any other evidence, is subject to evaluation in terms of relevance, admissibility and reliability. Like any other evidence, the expert opinion may be considered inadmissible (unreliable) evidence and not be used in evidence.

The legislator in the criminal procedural law did not define the standards for the concepts of "relevance" and "admissibility" of evidence. In Part 2 of Art. 75 of the Code of Criminal Procedure lists evidence that is inadmissible. From our point of view, there is a need for a separate scientific debate on the feasibility of introducing into the criminal procedure law clear concepts of "relevance", "admissibility", "reliability" and "sufficiency" of evidence, which will allow us to more accurately imagine the criteria for evaluating evidence.

If the expert opinion meets the requirements of the law for evidence, it may have an advantage over other evidence, for example, the expert's conclusions may override the testimony of the accused, the witness and others. This is due to the fact that the information obtained as a result of expert research is based on objective, generally accepted scientific and practical data in contrast to the information contained in these indications, which are only of a subjective nature.

CONCLUSION:

Considering the above, there is an urgent need to make such changes in federal legislation that would allow for a clearer regulation of the procedure for the

appointment of judicial expertise by judicial bodies, their evaluation by the court and the investigation to ensure the full implementation of the principle of equality and competition of parties during judicial proceedings.

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